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COMPARISON OF HYDROTHERMAL POTENTIAL INDICATORS IN THE CULTIVATED CENOSSES OF MOUNTAIN GRAY-BROWN SOILS ACCORDING TO VEGETATION DENSITY

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Abstract

The article presents a comparative analysis of the hydrothermal potential (HTP) in cultivated cenoses of mountain gray-brown soils located on the southeastern slope of the Lesser Caucasus, with particular emphasis on vegetation cover density. The aim of the study is to assess the hydrothermal regime of the soil environment and soil–climate interactions. The research was conducted using N.R. Suleymanov's methodology for determining HTP, and soil temperature and moisture were measured under field conditions using an EC-350 device. The results indicate that cultivated cenoses with dense vegetation cover are characterized by higher HTP values: soil moisture is retained for longer periods, and the temperature regime remains more stable. In contrast, areas without vegetation or with sparse plant cover exhibit lower moisture content and elevated temperatures in the upper soil horizons. It has been established that vegetation cover plays a crucial role in stabilizing the soil microclimate.

Keywords: Lesser Caucasus, mountain gray-brown soils, hydrothermal potential, cultivated cenosis, vegetation cover.

INTRODUCTION

Land resources constitute natural assets of strategic importance for agricultural production and environmental sustainability in any country [1]. The study of their genetic characteristics, formation conditions, and functional properties is of considerable relevance for the rational use of soils, the planning of reclamation measures, and the optimization of agroecosystems [2]. In this context, the investigation of specific soil types widespread in mountainous and foothill regions—particularly mountain gray-brown soils—is of both scientific and practical significance.

The hydrothermal regime plays a decisive role in soil formation processes. Together with soil moisture availability and thermal balance, it directly affects the dynamics of key pedogenic processes such as humification, mineralization, leaching, and sorption [3; 4; 5; 6]. During periods of increased moisture, the decomposition and transformation of organic matter within the soil profile intensify, whereas under dry conditions, more stable forms of humus tend to accumulate. In regions such as Agdere, characterized by low annual precipitation and high evaporation rates, the influence of these factors on soil development is particularly pronounced [7].

In soils used for agricultural purposes, soil formation is accompanied by transformations in genetic horizons, soil regimes, process dynamics, physicochemical properties, and structural organization. In soils subjected to anthropogenic impact, soil types and properties reflect the degree of cultural soil formation and land-use intensity.

Microprocesses occurring within the soil environment, their relationship with hydrothermal resources, and the structural stability of the soil profile necessitate a comprehensive analysis of soil–climate interactions. Under conditions of contrasting moisture regimes, intensified decomposition and humification processes, along with the stabilization of humus reserves, contribute to enhanced soil fertility [8; 9]. Such findings are essential for the ecological assessment and sustainable management of soils under specific geographical conditions.

The primary objective of this study is to analyze the geographical factors influencing soil formation in the southeastern Lesser Caucasus, with particular emphasis on the hydrothermal regime, hypsometric characteristics, and soil–climate relationships. In addition to examining the genetic features of the soils, the study seeks to determine their position within the landscape structure [10].

RESEARCH OBJECT AND METHOD

The study area is located on the southeastern slope of the Lesser Caucasus, in the direction of the village of Talysh in the Aghdere district of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The coordinates of the study area are 40°21'55" N and 46°55'08" E, with an elevation of approximately 246 meters above sea level, within a flat area.

The Aghdere district is part of the Karabakh economic region, which encompasses the southeastern slope of the Lesser Caucasus and is characterized by unique natural and climatic conditions.

Figure 1. General view of the agricultural landscape of the study area (clover crops)

The soil cover of the studied agricultural landscapes is represented by mountain gray-brown soils with a heavy clay texture. The formation and functioning of these soils under agricultural use are accompanied by transformations in their morphological, physicochemical, and hydrothermal properties.

The Agdere region is characterized by a moderately warm climate with dry winters and is classified within the semi-desert dry-steppe climatic zone. The mean annual air temperature and precipitation amount to 13.9 °C and 363 mm, respectively. The moisture coefficient (Ku) ranges from 0.3 to 0.5, and total solar radiation reaches 124–128 kcal/cm² [11].

Repeated field and laboratory investigations have established that the mean soil bulk density of mountain gray-brown soils throughout the profile is 1.23 g/cm³, as confirmed by statistical analysis of the obtained data. The soils of the experimental plot are characterized by a heavy clay texture, and their particle-size distribution is directly related to soil bulk density. In the agrocenosis, soil bulk density varies from 1.16 to 1.30 g/cm³. It is lower in the upper horizons and gradually increases with depth along the soil profile (Table 1).

Table 1

Physicochemical parameters of mountain gray-brown soils under agrocenosis conditions (0-25 cm layer)

Soil type	Horizon, cm	Soil density, g/cm ³	Average density by profile, g/cm ³
Mountain gray-brown	0-5	1.16	1,23
	5-10	1.19	
	10-15	1.23	
	15-20	1.27	
	20-25	1.30	

The research methodology was based on the determination and comparative analysis of the hydrothermal potential (HTP) of soil environments under cultivated communities (clover). HTP was calculated according to the method proposed by N.R. Suleimanov [12, 13]. The vertical distribution of soil temperature and moisture was examined under field conditions, and hydrothermal potential calculations were performed in triplicate to ensure data reliability.

To evaluate hydrothermal potential parameters formed under the influence of specific abiotic factors within prevailing climatic conditions, Suleimanov's HTP index was applied. According to this approach, potential soil temperature and soil moisture content, as affected by external climatic factors, are integrated into

a single HTP parameter, which makes it possible to determine boundary conditions and characterize the hydrothermal state of the soil environment.

Soil temperature and moisture were measured directly in the field using a modern multifunctional mobile EC-350 device (USA), operating on the "soil moment" principle. Soil reaction (pH) was determined using a KCB-300 device.

The experimental site was located within an agricultural landscape cultivated with clover on the flat southeastern slope of the Lesser Caucasus and was characterized by mountain gray-brown soils. The study employed an integrated set of field and laboratory methods typical of soil ecological research. Soil pits were excavated, and samples were collected with consideration of agricultural landscape differentiation. Laboratory analyses included determination of particle-

size distribution, humus content, soil acidity (pH), and hydrophysical properties. The obtained data were processed using standard statistical analysis methods.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The soil profile is characterized by the distribution of temperature and moisture (hydrothermal parameters) across the depth, which is an important factor directly influencing plant growth and development, irrigation regimes, and crop yields in agricultural systems. Different soil covers (with or without vegetation) significantly influence this distribution (Table 2).

During the study, air temperatures ranged from 32°C to 39°C. The soil surface temperature was 34°C.

An analysis of hydrothermal potential indicators demonstrated that vegetation density significantly influences the distribution of soil temperature, moisture,

and water reserves within the agrocenoses of the experimental site.

Under sparse vegetation (K-1), the mean soil temperature within the 0–25 cm layer was 31.58 °C, soil moisture averaged 31.98%, water reserves amounted to 21.58 mm, and the hydrothermal potential reached 642 snr (Kst = 0.7), indicating limited moisture retention capacity.

Under dense vegetation (K-2), soil temperature was lower (29.34 °C), while moisture content was substantially higher (60.96%); water reserves reached 40.08 mm, and the hydrothermal potential increased to 1130 snr (Kst = 1.4), reflecting a more favorable hydrothermal regime for plant development.

Table 2

Soil hydrothermal potential indicators determined by vegetation density in piedmont plain agrocenoses

Section	Depth, cm	Soil temperature, °C	Soil moisture, %	Water content, mm	HTP, snr	K _{st}
K-1 (sparse vegetation)	5	37,60	6,90	4,00	150	0,1
	10	34,70	42,80	25,47	884	0,7
	15	32,30	74,20	45,63	1474	1,4
	20	29,50	85,20	54,10	1596	1,8
	25	27,30	81,90	53,24	1453	2,0
	0-25 cm	32,28	58,20	36,49	1111	1,2
K-2 (dense vegetation)	5	31,30	4,30	2,49	78	0,1
	10	34,70	76,60	45,58	1582	1,3
	15	31,50	82,10	50,49	1590	1,6
	20	28,50	86,60	54,99	1567	1,9
	25	27,00	88,10	57,27	1546	2,1
	0-25 cm	30,60	67,54	42,16	1273	1,4
K-3 (without vegetation)	5	30,30	17,40	10,09	306	0,3
	10	31,80	55,70	33,14	1054	1,0
	15	31,40	75,50	46,43	1458	1,5
	20	29,70	85,20	54,10	1607	1,8
	25	28,50	88,00	57,20	1630	2,0
	0-25 cm	30,34	64,36	40,19	1211	1,3

In the bare area (K-3), soil temperature was elevated (33.76 °C), whereas moisture content and water reserves (31.50% and 21.17 mm, respectively) remained relatively low. The hydrothermal potential was 698 snr (Kst = 0.6), indicating comparatively unfavorable conditions. These findings demonstrate that dense vegetation contributes to the optimization of soil hydrothermal potential [10].

HTP values were highest under dense vegetation cover, ranging from 285 to 1588 snr. Under sparse vegetation, values ranged from 42 to 1588 snr, and in bare areas from 37 to 1606 snr. The weighted mean HTP values were 1130 snr for dense vegetation, 642 snr for sparse vegetation, and 698 snr for bare soil.

A comparative analysis of hydrothermal potential curves in cultivated cenoses across different vegetation densities indicates that the soil hydrothermal regime is strongly dependent on vegetation cover density and the degree of anthropogenic impact.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The hydrothermal potential of the soil environment was determined for cultivated cenoses of the Agdere district's gray-brown mountain soils based on vegetation density and soil profile depth, and a comparative analysis of the data was conducted.

2. HTP values are highest under dense vegetation cover and range from 285 to 1588 snr. Under sparse vegetation, values are lower—42 to 1588 snr—and in bare areas, 37 to 1606 snr. The weighted average HTP values were 1130 snr for dense vegetation, 642 snr for sparse vegetation, and 698 snr for bare areas, respectively.

3. Vegetation cover plays an important role in maintaining a stable hydrothermal regime in the soil.

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